

MODELING OF LAYERED OIL AND GAS-BEARING ENVIRONMENTS WITHIN THE SRIBNEN DEPRESSION BASED ON GRAVIMETRIC DATA

Kyshman-Lavanova T.

*Institute of Geophysics named after S.I. Subbotina
of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine*

ABSTRACT

Prospects for hydrocarbon accumulation at the Khortytsia site are associated with the presence of biohermic carbonate structures of considerable capacity. Based on the quantitative interpretation of gravimetric data, a layered model of the geological environment with a fixed density of rocks was built. The simulation results showed that the hypothesis about the decompression of rocks of the Visean carbonate plate is realistic. A number of negative anomalies can be connected precisely with hydrocarbon traps, which have been revealed by seismic and drilling data. The obtained results of the interpretation correlate with the conclusions of other researchers. The inversion of gravimetric data was performed by searching for Pareto-optimal solutions under conditions of uncertain a priori information.

Keywords: inverse problem of gravimetry, geological modeling, oil and gas.

Introduction

Predictions and searches for oil and gas deposits are always performed using various geophysical surveys. Along with seismic methods, which provide the most accurate results when determining the near-surface geology of the studied area, non-seismic methods, among which there is gravity exploration, are considered quite optimal in terms of time and cost.

Gravimetric data are informative both at the local and regional levels. The regional gravity field of the platforms has extended zones of thickening iso-anomalous – gravity ledges. In many cases, they fix tectonic faults on the surface of the foundation and associated flexures and shaft-like structures in the sedimentary cover - systems of oil and gas traps [3].

At the prospecting stage, the interpretation of gravimetric data helps to identify the conditions of occurrence and parameters of promising layers, to select local structures (anticlines, domes), which are of primary importance for prospecting drilling [8]. At the stage of detailing the identified promising objects, the identification of productive reservoir layers covered by caps, determination of the parameters of these layers can be added to the set of tasks.

For a high-quality and reliable assessment of the prospects of the oil and gas potential of the subsoil within any geological environment, it is necessary to clearly distinguish the forecasting objects both in space and in the section of the rocks that participate in the structure of this environment.

The vast majority of open deposits, which contain the main reserves of oil and gas in the lithosphere, are associated with geostructural objects, diverse in structure and genesis: anticlinal folds, domes, erosional protrusions, reefs, open structures (in the form of flexures, structural noses, monoclinals), which can be complicated by disjuncts, facies change of rocks, stratigraphic unconformities, salt dome tectonics, diapirism, mud volcanism, etc. [9].

Such a variety of forms of hydrocarbon deposits requires effective and dynamic mathematical models to describe the geological environment.

On the other hand, the qualitative and quantitative interpretation of gravimetric data allows obtaining some optimal mathematical model of the geology of the

studied area and graphic constructions of maps of anomalous components of the field and sections of three-dimensional models (the result of solving the inverse problem of gravity prospecting).

There are several approaches to the interpretation of gravimetric data and, accordingly, methods of solving inverse problems of gravimetry. However, the purely mathematical statement of the inverse problem must be supplemented with geologically meaningful components, that is, the method must be adapted to the problem of gravimetry and the peculiarities of the mathematical model and the criteria it must meet must be taken into account. In the inversion of gravimetric data, the practice of solving linear inverse problems is widespread. However, in the conditions of the search and exploration of hydrocarbons, when there are problems of interpreting the observed data caused by the presence of natural reservoirs of hydrocarbons (layered, massive or lithological), the use of linear problems is not always effective due to the multi-parameter nature and incorrectness of the problem.

The purpose of this work is to show that the previously proposed non-probabilistic approach to solving inverse problems and the approximation design of the contact surface for building a model of the geological environment works on real data for the purpose of finding hydrocarbon deposits, and the results of the interpretation of gravimetric data are correlated with the results of other researchers.

The basis of this work was the observed gravity data and some results of their interpretation, performed in the work [1].

Methods and mathematical constructions of geological modeling.

The inversion of gravimetric data is performed within the framework of a non-probabilistic approach, namely by searching for Pareto-optimal solutions in conditions of uncertain a priori information. The method allows to explore the parametric space for the presence of solutions and choose the optimal one. Uncertain a priori information is described using fuzzy sets. The method is described in detail in the work [5].

The geological environment is modeled in the class of three-dimensional contact surfaces [4].

Location and geological prerequisites for the prospects of a given area for hydrocarbons.

The studied area is located in the northwestern part of the Dnipro-Donetsk Zapadina (DDZ), namely in the south of Chernihiv region, Khortytsia settlement (Prylutsky district).

Despite the detailed and long-term study of the DDZ, there is no objective assessment of the hydrocarbon resources of the DDZ carbonate formations. As is known, the prospects for the discovery of new DDZ deposits are associated with traps of the non-anticlinal type of the Lower Visean carbonate complex. In the geological structure of the DDZ, two carbonate strata of the lower vise stand out over the entire territory of the depression, and only in the northwest and in the coastal zones are they replaced by terrigenous continental and subcontinental deposits [2].

Khortytsya square is located in the framing zone of the Sribne Depression (SD). The SD is confined to the northwestern segment of the axial zone of the DDZ and is clearly distinguished in the gravity and magnetic fields. It is a complex late Proterozoic-Paleozoic synclinal structure with a sedimentary cover of a wide stratigraphic and formation range [7]. Thus, in the early visage, a ring zone of development of rifogenic-carbonate bodies was formed on the border of the SD. They are surrounded by reef massifs with oil and gas-bearing carbonate reservoirs [6].

Based on the results of seismic exploration within the Sribnen depression, a number of structures were identified to which the explosive deposits can be attributed. The close location of a number of already discovered oil fields, the closest of which is the Hnidyntsiivskoye field, testifies to the high prospects of the oil and gas potential of the discovered structures.

Geological structure of the studied area.

In tectonic terms, the Khortytsya area is located in the southwestern part of the Sribne depression. In the relief of the foundation, it is limited to a gentle

monocline, which dips in the direction of the central part of the depression. The depth of occurrence of crystalline rocks within the area is 7500-8000 m [1].

According to the data of parametric drilling, the sedimentary layer is composed of Paleozoic, Mesozoic, and Cenozoic rocks. In the clay-carbonate stratum of the Visean Carboniferous stage, biohermic carbonate structures of greater capacity stand out, the so-called carbonate plate, with which prospects for hydrocarbon accumulation are associated. According to drilling data, the plate has a thickness of 60 to 120 m, and its lower limit can reach a depth of 4960 m. The carbonate plate consists of three layers of different composition. The lower (up to 30 m) is composed of clayey-silica-carbonate rocks with loose limestones, the middle (up to 70 m) - dense limestones with bioherm formations, the upper (up to 60 m) - dense clayey carbonates. Carbonate rocks in the lower and middle layers of the plate have the best filtering and storage properties.

The rocks of the strata within the Visean layer are not differentiated by density. Only the range of possible density values is specified: $(2.53-2.56) \cdot 10^3 \text{ kg/m}^3$.

Analysis of observed gravimetric data.

The observation field of gravity was obtained as a result of detailed high-precision gravimetric works on the Khortytsya square with a size of $4000 \cdot 2000 \text{ m}^2$. Shooting scale 1:50000. For interpretation, the gravity anomaly field in the Bouguet reduction is taken (Fig. 1). The result of the initial interpretation was a three-dimensional geodensity model of the geological environment [1].

In order to highlight local anomalies caused by Visean geological formations, the observation field was transformed by the method of averaging with radii of 500, 1000, and 2000 m. For further processing, a field of local anomalies with an averaging radius of 1000 m was used, which displayed both the general features of the transformed field and isolated local anomalies (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. Map of the observed gravity field in the Bouguet reduction (in mGal).

However, a qualitative analysis of local anomalies with averaging radii of 500 m and 1000 m makes it possible to draw important conclusions.

The field of local anomalies Δg with an averaging radius of 1000 m (Fig. 2) is represented by partially

negative anomalies with an intensity of up to - 0.50 mGal in the southwestern part of the area, and positive anomalies with an intensity of up to 0.40 mGal in the rest of the area.

Fig. 2. Map of local gravity field anomalies, in mGal. Averaging radius 1000 m. Scale 1:25000.

The bioherm structure assumed by the seismic survey data is covered by the negative and positive field Δg , but in some cases there is an agreement of its contours with the features of the anomalous gravity field.

The field of local anomalies with an averaging radius of 500 m (Figure 3), compared to the one described above, is more detailed. Its negative part covers most of the area, but unlike the previous

transformation, it is divided into a number of local anomalies, the intensity of which does not exceed 0.2 mGal. The positive field has the same character, however, the intensity of the latter is somewhat lower (up to 0.10 mGal). The contours of the bioherm building are quite clearly traced in the anomalous gravity field by the nature of the distribution of local anomalies of both signs.

Fig. 3. Map of local gravity field anomalies, in mGal. The averaging radius is 500 m.

Therefore, already at the stage of qualitative interpretation, from the distribution of the high-precision gravimetric field and the available geophysical and geological data, it can be assumed that ring gravimetric anomalies (that is, positive anomalies framed by negative ones) fix biohermic structures, which are promising for the content of hydrocarbon deposits.

Construction of an a priori model of the environment and its approximation design.

The structural model of the geological environment at the time of quantitative interpretation was built on the basis of geological information, seismic data, as well as the results of geodensity modeling performed in [1].

The model of the studied area contains a carbonate plate bounded by the roof and sole. The roof of the plate to be modeled is approximated by a contact surface that separates the upper boundary of the carbonate plate and the stratum rocks located above it. The lower limit of the slab is fixed at a depth of 4960 m (according to drilling data). A detailed description of the

approximation design for the contact surface is given in the work [4]. Since the model class of contact surfaces involves fixing some conditional reference level H_0 , it is logical to tie it to the lowest point of the carbonate plate – to its sole at a depth of 4960 m.

Then, anomalous disturbing masses of fixed density σ and thickness from 60 to 120 m are contained between the H_0 level and the roof of the carbonate plate, the relief of which must be determined. That is, from a mathematical point of view, a nonlinear inverse gravimetric problem is solved.

A rectangular area with a size of 4000*4000 m², with a step on the grid of 500 m, was chosen as the area of determination of the carbonate plate roof.

The points that are fixed in the observed anomalous field are located in the central sector of the selected area. In this case, the influence of the unaccounted asymptotic parts of the contact surface will be minimal.

At each point of the selected area, the surface deviates from the fixed level H_0 by an amount

$$Z = Z(\xi, \eta) = \sum_{j=1}^m \frac{Q1_j}{[1 + Q2_j(\xi - \xi_{oj})^2 + Q3_j(\eta - \eta_{oj})^2]^\alpha}, \quad (1)$$

where the values of the parameter α ($\alpha \div \frac{1}{2}; 1; 2$ or others) form various approximation constructions. $[(\xi_0, \eta_0)_j, j = 1, 2, \dots, m]$ – points of the definition area of the plate roof. The searched parameters are $Q1_j, Q2_j, Q3_j$, they determine the configuration of the surface relief at each grid point. In the initial models, these parameters are set to be the same and equal to 1 m.

The contact surface itself is determined by the function $H(\xi, \eta) = H_0 - Z(\xi, \eta)$.

It is important to note that since the Oz axis is directed upwards in the selected coordinate system, the depth values on the maps will always be negative, although in the description of the problem, when it comes to depth, we omit the "minus" sign.

Since the rocks of the carbonate plate on average can be both loose and compacted (relative to other rocks), it is advisable to consider both variants of the a priori geodensity model and analyze the results of the interpretation.

It should be noted that the structure of the upper part of the section is unknown, and its influence was not removed from the anomalous observed field. On the other hand, local anomalies of small extent in the observed field have a near-surface nature. Therefore, the results of minimizing the discrepancy between the observed and theoretical fields should not be reduced to minimum values.

Results of the interpretation of the field of local anomalies for different densities of rocks of the carbonate plate.

The first option. The rocks of the carbonate plate are loosened with a density of $2,53 \cdot 10^3 \text{ kg/m}^3$. The density of the surrounding rocks is $2,56 \cdot 10^3 \text{ kg/m}^3$.

Fig. 4 The upper map is the field of local gravity anomalies in mGal, the averaging radius is 1000 m. The lower map is the result of the interpretation of the field of local anomalies, the isoline of the relief of the contact surface with the starting point at a depth of 4960 m.

The result of solving the inverse problem is a model of a carbonate plate (Fig. 4). As can be seen from Fig. 4, there is a coordinated extension of the isoline of the relief of the roof of the contact surface and the isolines of the anomalous field. The minimum values of the anomalous field correspond to the areas with the maximum power of the plate, that is, the areas with the maximum concentration of loose masses. The plate thickness ranges from 60 to 120 m, which also agrees with a priori data.

It should be noted that the iterative process of finding a solution was stopped at the value of the

discrepancy function of 39.41 mGal^2 , since further selection did not improve the result due to the unaccounted influence of geological masses located in the surface layer.

Therefore, the assumption of loosening of the carbonate plate is quite realistic.

The second option. The rocks of the carbonate plate are compacted, that is, they have an average density $2,56 \cdot 10^3 \text{ kg/m}^3$. Other rocks – $2,53 \cdot 10^3 \text{ kg/m}^3$.

Fig. 5. The upper map of the isolines is the field of local anomalies, the averaging radius is 1000 m. The lower map is the selected topography of the carbonate plate under the condition of its excess density of 0.03 kg/m^3 , the sole of the plate is at a depth of 4960 m.

Having analyzed the field of local anomalies, it can be seen that the extension of the zone of minimum values is observed along the diagonal of the map from the northwest to the southeast. The isoline map of the relief of the contact surface shows that the power of the plate acquires minimum values in the approximate direction to the zone of extension of minimum field values, which has some logical explanation. Since in this case the plate is considered to be denser than the surrounding rocks, the excess density is compensated by the reduction of the plate power in the area of negative field values. That is, the slab seems to be "trying to sink" under the zone of negative anomalies,

and the side parts of the slab relative to the indicated subsidence diagonal have a greater power. However, since there is no clear agreement between the direction of the diagonal of the minimum values of local anomalies and the direction of subsidence of the plate, it can be assumed that the considered version of the compacted carbonate plate is not realistic.

Conclusion.

Thus, according to the results of gravimetric modeling, the hypothesis about the loosening of the rocks of the Visean carbonate plate is realistic. The fact that with a fixed density of rocks, the relief of the desired contact surface is formed in accordance with

the field of local anomalies and the values of geometric parameters are within the permissible limits according to a priori information, indicates a high probability of the formation of hydrocarbon accumulation zones in the investigated area. A number of negative anomalies can be connected precisely with hydrocarbon traps, which have been detected by seismic and drilling data.

The used approximation design for modeling the geological environment has shown its effectiveness, optimally combining the number of parameters and the detail of the description of the contact surface. Therefore, in addition to modeling tasks, such an approximation construction can be used in the tasks of outlining deposits and estimating hydrocarbon reserves.

It should be noted that when determining the location of exploratory and exploratory wells, it is necessary to take into account the results of the interpretation of high-precision gravimetric survey data in combination with other information.

References

1. Anikeev S.G., Shurovsky O.D. Prediction of oil and gas prospective areas within the southwestern part of the Sribnen depression of the Dnieper-Donets depression based on the data of gravity exploration // *Geodynamics*, 1(18), 2015. P. 86-98.
2. Bilyk A.O. Stratigraphy, correlation and prospects of oil and gas bearing of Tournai and Visey deposits of the Dnieper-Donetsk basin / Bilyk A.O., Vakarchuk G.I., Ivanyshyn V.A. – Chernihiv: “Chernihivski oberegy”. 2002. 110 p.
3. Berezkin V.M. Application of gravity exploration to search for oil and gas fields. Nedra. Moscow. 1973. 264 p.
4. Bulakh E.G., Kyshman-Lavanova T.N. Another approximation approach to solving inverse problems of gravimetry in the class of three-dimensional contact surfaces // *Geophysical Journal*. 2006. N. 2, V. 28. P. 54-62.
5. Kyshman-Lavanova T.N. Pareto-optimal solutions of the inverse problem of gravimetry in the class of three-dimensional contact surfaces // *Geophysical journal*. 2020. N 6, V. 42. P. 207-221.
6. Lukin A.E., Chepyl P.M., Shpak P.F., Machulina S.A. About Srednevizey Srebnensky megaatoll // *Dokl. Academy of Sciences of Ukraine*. 1994. N. 3. P. 101-105.
7. Lukin A.E., Shestopalov V.M. Annular tectonomagmatogenic structures in zones of increased geodynamic instability – first priority objects of the search for hydrogen deposits // *Geophysical journal*. 2021. N. 4, V. 43. P. 3-41.
8. Megerya V. M. Possibilities and perspectives of the application of non-seismic methods for the search of accumulated hydrocarbons and the geosoliton concept of their formation / V. M. Megerya, V. G. Filatov, V. I. Starostenko, I. N. Korchagin, A. M. Lobanov, Yu. V. Glasko, M. Yu. Volotskov, S. A. Skachkov // *Geophysical journal*. 2012. N 3, V. 34. P. 4-21.
9. Monchak L.S., Omelchenko V.G. Fundamentals of oil and gas geology: Textbook for universities. Ivano-Frankivsk: Fakel. 2004. 276 p.